

Fatphobia in the news: a textual-discursive analysis of discursive representation and enunciative responsibility /

A gordofobia no gênero notícia em uma análise textual-discursiva da representação discursiva e da responsabilidade enunciativa

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ABSTRACT

This article aims to analyse how the discursive representation and the (non) assumption of enunciative responsibility are manifested in a piece of news about a fatphobia episode published in Claudia magazine in February, 2020, considering the management of points of view in the text by the first speaker-enunciator (S1/E1). For this, we assume a perspective which articulates the analysis plans of the text and the discourse, focusing in the semantic-pragmatic, enunciative and sociodiscursive, under the approach of the Textual Discursive Analysis (ADAM, 2019, 2011, 2010) and the point of view theory (RABATEL, 2016a, 2016b). The paper was developed from a case study, following a qualitative approach and was based in the following categories: referencing and modification to the DRs; and the modalities and the indication of mediation charts to the ER; the socio-discursive analysis and interdiscourse, to understand the ideological position of S1/E1 and the relation of voices reported in the text. In the analysis, we show that the management of voices by the S1/E1 is, on one hand, prototypical of the genre, when this discursive instance focuses on other enunciators and assigns them the responsibility for the content of the POV; but, on the other hand, the lexical choices (referential and modifiers), the organization of linguistic signs (verbal and imagery) argumentatively guide the text, leading the interpretant to perceive the different DRs and the links of responsibility between S1/E1 and the POVs of the victim of the fatphobia episode and with those who expressed their support and acceptance.

KEYWORDS: News; Viewpoints; Discursive representation; Enunciative responsibility; Fatphobia.

RESUMO

Este artigo analisa o modo como se manifesta a representação discursiva (Rd) e a (não) assunção da responsabilidade enunciativa (RE) em uma notícia sobre um episódio de gordofobia publicada na revista Claudia, em fevereiro de 2020, considerando a gestão dos pontos de vista (PDV) no texto pelo locutor-enunciador primeiro (L1/E1). Para isso, articulamos os planos de análise do texto e do discurso, com foco nas dimensões semântico-pragmática, enunciativa e sociodiscursiva, sob a ancoragem da Análise Textual dos Discursos (ADAM, 2019, 2011, 2010) e da teoria do ponto de vista (RABATEL, 2016a, 2016b). O trabalho foi desenvolvido a partir de um estudo de caso, seguindo uma abordagem qualitativa, e norteou-se pelas seguintes categorias: a referência e a modificação, para análise das Rd; as modalidades e as indicações de quadros mediadores, para análise da RE; as formações sociodiscursivas e o interdiscurso, para compreensão da posição ideológica do L1/E1 e da relação entre as vozes reportadas no texto. Na análise, mostramos que a gestão das vozes pelo L1/E1 é, de um lado, prototípico do gênero notícia, nos momentos em que essa instância discursiva focaliza outros enunciadores e atribui a eles a responsabilidade pelo conteúdo dos PDV; mas, de outro lado, as escolhas lexicais (referenciais e modificadores), a organização dos signos linguísticos (verbais e imagéticos) orientam argumentativamente o texto, conduzindo o interpretante a perceber as diferentes Rd e os elos de responsabilização do L1/E1 com o PDV da vítima do episódio de gordofobia e com aqueles que se manifestaram em seu apoio e acolhimento.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Notícia; Pontos de vista; Representação discursiva; Responsabilidade enunciativa; Gordofobia.

1 Introduction

This paper focuses on the problem of how the interactional construction of points of view about the different social events that surround us takes place in the Brazilian journalistic media, paying particular attention to the “role of the enunciator”, in the sense as understood by Rabatel (2016a, 2016b, 2013). , 2009), because it is through this discursive notion that we can analyze, among many other aspects, the polyphonic unfolding of utterances, the representations of objects of discourse and the enunciative responsibility, as proposed by Adam (2011).

Looking at this problem is due to the assumption that the way of building this type of knowledge (journalistic information) interferes with the way subjects position themselves in the face

of facts. In other words, we assume that the discursive strategies of the speaker-enunciator affect the actions of their interlocutors and that the qualitative and critical reading of information can allow these individuals, as interpreting subjects, to achieve a better position in the unequal relations of knowledge/power.

The institutionalized means to keep us informed of events of different natures (political, economic, social, etc.) is still the journalistic media. With the popularity of digital social media, we were introduced to new ways of propagating news and new ways of interacting with its content, as print, radio and television media began to coexist with the online form. We have at your disposal the most varied digital news portals (national, regional, local, whether big or little renowned, serious or amateur), in addition to pages, blogs, channels, podcasts etc., which, due to the platform where are hosted, allow reactions such as like, comment, share, save, among others.

Given the nature of language, we know that no discourse is neutral. Thus, the discourses that circulate in the media are also constructed from a certain ideological intention and are inscribed in a certain axiological position (VOLÓCHINOV, 2017), characterizing a type of knowledge that produces effects of power (CHARAUDEAU, 2013). We also know that the production of discourse, in these media, is not exempt from social criticism, because, in addition to being able to question what competence such media or professionals have to inform, nowadays it is possible to require that a newspaper review its own value systems.

In the context of digital social media, for example, situations of retraction of information vehicles have been increasingly frequent in the face of an act of speech considered to be of bad tone by the interlocutors. The Brazilian journalistic media itself has often been accused of serving the interests of certain groups, especially when it addresses controversial situations that deal with social minorities or situations of prejudice. Journalistic media professionals can even be targets of what has been designated today as “cancel culture”, a kind of punishment in and through social networks, not only directed at artists, celebrities, but also at other known or famous people.

We can say, then, that the quality of access to knowledge is increasingly evident with the dissemination of information and links about the most diverse topics via social networks, since any individual with a wi-fi network can access information, share it and publicly give opinion on the facts. In this way, the media, through social networks, has a prominent role in the dissemination of news and in the discussion of topics of general interest.

It is precisely because we do not assume “a naive point of view regarding information” (CHARAUDEAU, 2013, p. 34) – that of believing in transparency or, more generally, in the one-to-

one correspondence between language and reality, as if this was evident -, that we think it is relevant to reflect on the nature of non-transparency and non-evidence from the speaker's point of view (instance that reports the fact), since he or she does not only utters the information, but is also assimilated to the enunciators that he or she puts on the scene in the piece of news ; therefore, he or she positions himself or herself, argues and, consequently, exerts particular effects of knowledge/power in the social environment.

Thinking about the informative and journalistic genres, a group to which the news genre belongs, requires thinking, as well, in objectivity and impartiality. However, as we believe that no discourse is impartial, being always loaded with the speaker-enunciator's intentions, we highlight, in this work, the relationship between point of view, discursive representation and enunciative responsibility, based on the theoretical assumptions of Textual Analysis of Discourses – ATD, understanding, according to Adam (2011, p. 113), that “every discursive representation [Dr] is the expression of a point of view [...] and that the illocutionary value derived from the argumentative orientation is inseparable from the link between the meaning of an utterance and a significant enunciative activity” that the text invites to (re)construct.

Enunciative responsibility rests as an inseparable element in this relationship, given that every point of view presupposes a discursive instance that assumes its propositional content or attributes it to another instance. Therefore, it is up to the ER to take a position in the discourse, even that of alleged neutrality, theoretically possible, but that does not last long (RABATEL, 2009).

In this direction, since we are not the first to take a genre of media discourse as an object of study, we delimited as a general objective for this work to analyze the way in which the discursive representation (Dr) and the (non) assumption of enunciative responsibility (RE) are manifested in a news article¹ about an episode of fatphobia published in *Claudia* magazine, in February 2020. More precisely, we focus on the management of points of view (POV) in the text by the first speaker-enunciator (L1/E1), verifying how this discursive instance manifests the enunciative erasure for the sake of the objectivity of the language to which it has to submit in the journalistic sphere, but how, at the same time, it gives signs of its subjective positioning, through the linguistic choices.

In addition to anchoring in the DTA (ADAM, 2019, 2011, 2010), we are guided by the theory of point of view (RABATEL, 2016a, 2016b, 2013, 2009) and we establish a dialogue with Bakhtinian

¹ The piece of news is part of a group of journalistic texts about fatphobia. The selected sample was taken from the corpus of one of the authors' Phd research, but, in this article, we offer a different analytical treatment.

reflections about the ideological nature of the sign, dialogism and discourse genres, as well as with scholars who adhere to these theoretical perspectives. In methodological terms, the work is qualitative in nature and was developed from a case study. We assume a perspective that articulates the plans of analysis of text and discourse, focusing on the semantic-pragmatic, enunciative and socio-discursive dimensions, guided by the following categories: referencing and modification, for the analysis of Rd; the modalities and indications of mediators, for analysis of the RE; the socio-discursive formations and the interdiscourse, to understand the ideological position assumed by S1/E1, as well as the relationship between the reported voices in the materiality of saying and the socio-historical conditions of production of meanings.

In the following pages, we firstly bring a synthesis of the concepts and theoretical postulates assumed as basic, pointing out the methodological developments for the work; secondly, a contextualization of the conditions of production of the clipped piece of news as a corpus of analysis; then, we carried out a textual-discursive analysis of the production of meanings, centered on the interactional dimension of points of view, and finally the concluding comments.

2 Theoretical-methodological framework

Due to space limitations, some concepts and guiding postulates of this work are taken up again in an integrated way in the corpus analysis section, especially those that refer to a dialogical and ideological conception of language. The other reason is because we consider that the two theoretical frameworks from which we adopted the categories of analysis – the TDA and the enunciative and pragmatic approach to points of view – are influenced by the interactionist understanding of language thought in Bakhtin's and his Circle's writings. This is evident, as demonstration, in the following passages from Adam's (2011) work:

This operation of interpretive construction [resuming the analysis of Breton's work] of the meaning of an utterance passes through a movement that goes from one text to another, from texts to texts, in a defined set of corpus of texts. This corpus of texts is built on the analysis of a network, giving the utterances a meaning that exceeds the limits of the text. (ADAM, 2011, p. 58, our translation).

[...] an elementary utterance is linked to one or several others and/or summons one or several others in response or as a simple continuation. (ADAM, 2011, p. 109, our translation).

When dealing with the enunciative instruments of the point of view, Rabatel (2016a, p. 87) explicitly assumes the inscription of his works in the field of dialogism, stating: “[...] the discourses are always crossed by the speech of others, constructed with and against them, in interlocutory and interdiscursive dialogism”. The author admits this social dimension of every discourse and, at the same time, its unique character, as we can attest in the following words:

But the very fact that, in his speech, a speaker/enunciator echoes in a certain different POV, in such a collective POV, in such a doxic POV, does not exclude that the radically socialized dimension of exchanges passes through his/her voice... even if it overtakes it. Consequently, when we point to the singular origin of the enunciators, this cannot occur by denying the social dimension of their discourses, but, on the contrary, with the purpose of better thinking about the discursive outlines of the dialectic of the singular and the social at the very heart of speech. (RABATEL, 2016a, p. 87-88, our translation).

In this sense, when we follow these authors' postulations, we are in line with Bakhtinian dialogism, understanding that discourse is “born” in the relationship with other discourses, in response to them, constitutively, “because every concrete discourse (enunciation) finds that object to which is always turned, so to speak, already discredited, contested, evaluated, enveloped by its dark fog or, on the contrary, illuminated by the discourses of others who have already spoken about it. [...] (BAKHTIN, 2002, p. 86).

We understand, therefore, that enunciation is a concrete activity and not a linguistic abstraction, and that its most fundamental characteristic is the result of the process of social interaction, carried out by historically situated subjects (VOLOCHÍNOV/BAKHTIN, 2011). The utterance, in turn, as a product of the enunciation and unit of human communication, constitutes itself as “a link in the chain of discursive communication. It is the speaker's active position in this or that field of object and meaning. (BAKHTIN, 2011, p. 289).

The vision of Bakhtin and the Circle also guides us towards an understanding of the sign and consciousness as being of an inter-individual and socio-ideological nature, because “everything that is said, what is expressed is outside the speaker's 'soul', does not belong only to him” (BAKHTIN, 2011, pp. 327-328). In this context, we apprehend that the “abode” of the word is not the mind (corresponding to the Saussurean conception of language as a treasure deposited in the mind of each individual by the practice of speech), or the (psychological) consciousness of any individual (related to the generativist conception language as an internalized knowledge or competence resulting from an innate device, installed in the brain by genetic endowment), but the social group, after all, individual conscience is a social and ideological fact, in such a way that “if

we deprive the conscience of its signic and ideological content, there will be absolutely nothing left of it” (VOLÓCHINOV, 2017, p. 98, our translation).

That said, we move on to a synthesis that puts the two theoretical frameworks that guide the present work, the TDA and the point of view approach, in a dialogic relationship, specifying the concepts that most directly interest us.

3 The textual discourse analysis

Textual Discourse Analysis (TDA) is a theory of co(n)textual production of meanings proposed by Jean-Michel Adam, a researcher with vast experience and scientific production in the area, widely known for his work on textual sequences. TDA is founded on the idea that the text, being a complex empirical object, could justify the use of different theories for its description, but Adam (2011) believes that the existence of a theory of this object integrated into the wider domain of discourse is generally necessary.

According to the author, DTA is a set theory “with the aim of thinking about text and discourse in new categories.” (ADAM, 2011, p. 24, our translation). The term “set” indicates the proposed articulation with other language sciences, whose concepts are eventually borrowed, but mainly suggests the idea that such concepts are redefined in a “new theoretical framework” and with an “indispensable coherence.” (ADAM, 2011, p. 25, our translation). The term “co(n)text” is used by the author to warn that “the interpretation of isolated utterances is based both on the (re)construction of utterances on the left and/or right (co-text) and on the operation of contextualization, which consists of imagining a situation of utterance that makes the utterance considered possible. (ADAM, 2011, p. 53, our translation).

From a theoretical-methodological point of view, DTA is inserted as a subdomain of Discourse Analysis (DA), approaching more specifically the DA model practiced by Dominique Maingueneau. In this way, it proposes to separate and at the same time complement the tasks of Textual Linguistics (TL) and this broader framework of analysis of discursive practices, which is given by the articulation of its objects of study. In DTA, the text is examined as a historically situated discursive practice, being inseparable from the conditions of production and the genre that regulate it.

Bearing this in mind, in the analysis of the corpus of this work, we focused our attention on both the text levels and the discourse levels, as specified below:

Picture 1: Levels or plans of textual and discourse analysis.

Source: Adam (2011, p. 61).

Thus, we consider the news in its co(n)text of production, as a language act that aims at an action, projected onto its interlocutors (L1 and L2), related to a given social place, and, therefore, linked to certain socio-discursive formations, having their concrete realization from a text, which, in turn, meets the normative stabilizations of the genre, in all its aspects (L3). The news text, which meaning possibilities are constructed according to these production conditions, presents a texture (L4, composed of propositions, statements and periods), a compositional structure (L5, formed by the sequences and text plane), a semantic content (L6, which builds the discursive representation), an enunciative dimension (L7, in which the enunciative responsibility and polyphonic cohesion are located) and, also, an illocutionary force (L8, responsible for the speech acts and for the argumentative orientation).

In this direction, we intend to reflect on the implications of the construction of the journalistic text, specifically of the news genre, regarding the procedures of enunciative erasure, related to the character of “objectifying enunciation” (RABATEL, 2016a) typical of this genre, but also on how much the particular management of the voices and the linguistic choices of the speaker-enunciator reveal a subjective position towards the points of view attributed to others, and how this is(not) marked in the text, in view of the communicative purposes.

In the text dimension, our focus is on the semantic and enunciative levels, regarding the discursive representation and enunciative responsibility, as well as in the L8, as we consider the

role of the speaker-enunciator's choices for the argumentative orientation of the utterances and their illocutionary force. In the dimension of discourse, within the broader conditions of production, socio-discursive formations and interdiscourse gain greater importance in our analysis.

Next, we deal more precisely with the two central categories of analysis, in an integrated way with the notion of point of view.

4 Discursive representation

Currently, we are experiencing a process of deconstruction of pre-established concepts and paradigms in the various socio-discursive situations in which we are inserted. This deconstruction brings up debates about the body, race, gender, sexuality, in the most diverse communicational circumstances. We are particularly interested in the clashes and points of view brought through the media, in order to better understand how this occurs in this sphere of contemporary society.

Bearing this issue in mind, we first return to Orlandi (2007), in response to the question of the construction of meanings, in the relationship established with a given discursive formation: “[...] we can say that meaning does not exist in itself, but it is determined by the ideological positions risen in the socio-historical process in which words are produced. Words change their meaning according to the positions of those who use them.” (ORLANDI, 2007, p. 42-42). Thus, the ideological position of the speaker-enunciator (journalist, in the specific context of this article) and the socio-historical process (of the more contemporary debate on issues related to the body) will contribute to the construction of discursive representations.

The discursive representation (Rd) is situated between the dimensions of the proposition-utterance, at the semantic level of the textual analysis proposed by Adam (2011), as is clear in this passage of his work:

every uttered proposition has a descriptive value, the discursive activity of reference semantically constructs a representation, a communicable object of discourse. This semantic micro-universe presents itself, minimally, as a theme or object of discourse and the development of a predication about it. The simplest form is the structure that associates a noun phrase with a verb phrase, but from a semantic point of view, a proposition can very well be reduced to a noun and an adjective. (ADAM, 2011, p. 113-114, our translation).

The proposition, cited by the author, is a statement, which links a noun to a verb or adjective, resulting from a discursive activity of referencing. This Discursive Representation is built

by the speaker-enunciator according to an intentionality and according to his way of relating in the world, with his culture:

It is the interpretant that builds the Dr from the utterances (schematization), in terms of its own purposes (objectives, intentions) and its psychosocial representations of the situation, the enunciator and the world of the text, as well as its cultural assumptions [. ..] (ADAM, 2011, p. 114, our translation).

However, a certain Dr desired by the speaker-enunciator will only be assimilated by the interlocutor when he understands the objectives of the speaker and the context of the utterance. That is, the Dr will only be confirmed or not, depending on the previous knowledge to be activated during the textual interpretation.

In this article, the focus was given, specifically, to two textual categories of Dr, the referencing and the modification (located in the predication), as we delimited in the table below:

Table 1: Categories of discursive representation: referencing and modification

CATEGORY	CONCEPTS	LINGUISTIC MARKS
Referencing	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- It is a language activity performed by subjects through texts.- It results from a dynamic strategic processing whose discursive and intersubjective development expresses agreements and disagreements.- It is the designation of referents (things, objects, subjects of actions, processes), so it has the property of naming the participants in the process of verbal action.	Nouns and pronouns that refer to the subject of the proposition.
The modification	<ul style="list-style-type: none">- It lives up to the qualities attributed to the referents (discourse objects) established by the referencing.- Presents the properties or qualities of both referents and predications, and can be subdivided into modification of referencing and modification of predication.	Class or qualification expressions and attributes. Adjectives and verbal circumstances.

Source: elaborated by the authors of this article, based on Queiroz (2013)

The choice of referencing is because it introduces or resumes the enunciators in the news, that is, it shows how these subjects interact in relationships of agreement, disagreement or “neutrality”. In the case of modification, it is the category that will present the characteristics

attributed to the subjects present in the text, and the consequent construction of an image, which is valid for our reflection on the discourse on the fat body.

5 Enunciative responsibility

As well as the discursive representation, the enunciative responsibility (RE) and the point of view are dimensions of the proposition-utterance (Pic. 2), which is, according to Adam (2011), a syntactic-semantic micro-unit or elementary textual unit distinct from sentence (object of grammatical analysis), for marking the nature of the product of an utterance (utterance) and for being constitutively linked to other utterances:

Picture 2: Dimensions of the proposition-utterance²

Source: Adam (2011, p. 111).

The proposition-statement is conceived, then, according to not only linguistic (syntactic) criteria, but also to semantic-pragmatic and enunciative ones. In this sense, it is a minimal utterance, the expression of a point of view effectively realized in a context that constructs discursive representations of the objects of discourse and plays a fundamental role in the argumentative orientation of the text, due to its illocutionary value. When we focus our analysis on

² Enunciative Responsibility of Instance Point of View [PoV] B L7; Connection with a previous cotext (said or implicit) or an intertext; A (L6) Reference of a discursive representation constructed by the propositional content [p]; C (L8) illocutionary value [F-C2] resulting of the argumentative potentials of the utterances [Or-arg-C1]; Connection with an afterwards cotext (said or implicit).

ER, we are concerned not only with the identification of the enunciative instance in the origin of the points of view, but also, and mainly, with the linguistic operations carried out by the S1/E1 in the textual materiality to signal the degree of involvement with the content of the proposition-utterance and to construct discursive representations of the objects of discourse.

According to the theoretical framework highlighted here, the ER and the point of view (PoV, abbreviation for Adam) are not separated, being, therefore, within the scope of polyphony. When managing the voices in the text, “the utterances can thus not be assumed by the speaker-narrator” (ADAM, 2011, p. 115), as this instance can attribute them to the PoV of another enunciator and to another source, signaling this in different ways, with language units in certain portions of the text. In this case, the L1/E1 exempts itself from responsibility, either by linking the propositions to an anonymous PoV of common opinion or by attributing it to an “authority”, “witness”, “citizen”, among other sources, thus expressing the phenomenon of mediative, which, according to Guentcheva (1994), means that a certain textual zone is dependent on another source of knowledge (epistemic mediation) or of perception (perceptual mediation).

So, it is possible for the S1/E1 to demarcate the enunciative distance in relation to the PoV from another instance, due to certain argumentative purposes, such as the refutation of this PoV, intending to limit its truth. The language units capable of marking the degree of ER of a proposition are grouped by Adam (2011) into the following categories: person indices, spatial and temporal deictics, verb tenses, modalities, different types of speech representation, indications of mediating frames, autonymic modalization phenomena, indications of a support of perception and reported thoughts.

Each of these categories opens up a dialogue with other approaches to the field of language, hence our use of theoretical reflections by Rabatel (2017, 2016a, 2016b, 2013, 2009) regarding the point of view (abbreviated POV by the aforementioned author), which is designated, in linguistics, as “every utterance that predicts information about no matter what object of discourse, giving not only information about the object (relating to its denotation), but also about the way in which the enunciator observes the object, thus expressing a POV”. (RABATEL, 2017, p. 43). The author fundamentally says that “[...] to analyze a point of view is to recover, on the one hand, the contours of its propositional content and, on the other hand, its enunciative source, even when this is implicit, from the attribution of referents and the assemblages of sentences in a text [...]” (RABATEL, 2016a, p. 71).

Among many other aspects that we could take up here, it is especially relevant to understand that

the non-RE is not the counterpart of the RE, because the imputation is the one who plays this role. It is at the lower level of pragmatic exploration of imputations that L1/E1 needs to know if he or she is at odds with the imputed POV, if he or she considers it, without taking sides, explicitly (what we call “neutrality” or RE zero), or if he is in accordance with the POV. (RABATEL, 2016a, p. 94-95).

As we can see, three possibilities of involvement of the S1/E1 with the content of the POV attributed to other enunciators are admitted: an “almost ER”, in cases where there is the imputation of the POV followed by the manifestation of the agreement by the S1/E1, that is, it is, although this enunciative instance is not the source of the saying, it takes sides and expresses the ER, through the adhesion to the POV of the enunciator according to (e2); disagreement, when there is a refutation of the POV; and neutrality, when it is not possible to define what the S1/E1 thinks in relation to the imputed POV. We have already said that, for the author, neutrality has a temporary duration, since “departing from his saying does not indicate an absence of PEC [prise en charge énonciative], but a tactic of legitimacy that consists of relying on an external responsible” (RABATEL, 2009, p. 33).

For the refinement of these different ways of positioning the S1/E1 in the contexts of imputation, Rabatel (2016b) proposes the enunciative postures (Fig. 3), which gives us more precision in understanding the interactional dimension of the points of view and the role of the enunciator in this process (RABATEL, 2013).

Picture 3: The web of relations between consensus and dissensus

Source: Rabatel (2016b, p. 203). Available in: <http://periodicos.uesc.br/index.php/eideia/article/view/1328/1089>.

Understanding that there are intermediate states or a kind of gradation between the poles of consensus and dissent, the author distinguishes the enunciative postures as follows:

co-enunciation is a concordant agreement, that is, as a true co-enunciation, *co-construction by the speakers of a common and shared POV*, which engages them as enunciators. *Over-enunciation* corresponds to discordant agreement, *as the unequal co-construction of a dominant POV is inscribed in an apparent form of agreement, deporting the new meaning.* [...] *As for the understatement*, it stems from concordant disagreement, since the unequal co-construction of a dominated POV again says that *the effectively co-constructed POV is not shared by the two enunciators*, and that they make this disagreement understands their will or without their realization. (RABATEL, 2016b, p. 203, emphasis added, our translation).

Considering these theoretical devices, within the scope of TDA and point of view theory, we can think that, in the genres of journalistic discourse, such as news and reporting, the speaker therefore marks linguistically and strategically, the origin of the information given, as a way to guarantee effects of truth and credibility. It does not happen in the same way with the opinion article and the editorial, in which it is important to know what the S1/E1 thinks about the points of view of others that he or she puts on the scene to support his or her own; It is important to know exactly where you speak, your convictions on a topic, your values, etc.

Due to the set of categories and linguistic marks likely to indicate the degree of ER, we delimit, in this work, the modalities and indications of mediating (or mediative) frameworks. The choice of these categories, in particular, refers to the fact that the journalistic discourse is sometimes characterized as informative and other times as opinionated, and there may be the imputation of the ER, with the distance of the journalist, through the indication of mediators, but also appreciative valuations that, masked under the supposed objectivity of the informative report, reveal the social horizon of the newspaper (its worldview, its values), for which the journalist can pass for a simple spokesperson.

For the purposes of synthesis, we grouped the linguistic marks referring to the modalities and the mediative, as follows:

Table 2: Linguistic marks of modalities and indications and mediating frameworks.

CATEGORY	LINGUISTIC MARKS
Modalities	Major syntactic-semantic modalities: Thetics (assertion and denial) Hypothetical (actual) fictional and

	<p>Hyperthetic (exclamation)</p> <p>objective modalities</p> <p>intersubjective modalities</p> <p>Subjective modalities</p> <p>Verbs and Adverbs of Opinion</p> <p>Affective, evaluative and axiological lexemes</p>
<p>Indication of intermediate frames</p>	<p>Markers as second, according to and for</p> <p>Modalization by a verb tense as the future tense</p> <p>Choosing a speech attribution verb as they claim, it seems</p> <p>Reformulations of the type is, in fact, in fact, and even in any case</p> <p>Opposition of the type some think (or say) that X, we think (say) that Y, etc.</p>

Source: made by the authors of this article. Adapted (a clipping) from Passeggi et al. (2010, p. 300-301)

The modality operation already appeared in Culioli's (1990) reflections, meaning the expression from the enunciator's point of view, assuming or distancing himself or herself from what he or she enunciates, depending on the assigned modal. In order to better understand this category for the analysis of ER, we refer to the work of Neves (2012), who, based on the aforementioned author, conceives the modality as "the result of the location of the predicative relationship regarding the parameter S0, subject of the enunciation", and thus characterizes "the point of view of the enunciating subject on what he or she enunciates; assuming the constructed knowledge or moving away from it, depending on the modal value that will be assigned to it." (NEVES, 2012, p. 69, our translation). Therefore, for purposes of signaling the degree of ER, the speaker-enunciator manifests more or less the assumption of the predicate content, that is, he or she can validate or not the predicative relations (CULIOLI, 1990).

In our analysis of the modality, we also rely on Neves (2012), who proposes three types of modal values: epistemic, deontic and appreciative. The author classifies these values as follows: a) the epistemic value: "corresponds to the realization that a certain state of affairs IS or IS NOT"; b) the deontic value: "corresponds to the desire that a certain state of things IS or IS NOT"; c) the appreciative value: "corresponds to the appreciation of a state of affairs as DESIRABLE or UNDESIRABLE." (NEVES, 2012, p. 70-71, our translation). It is worth mentioning that the author still classifies the modalities of epistemic value as a gradation, which expressions may or may not increase the enunciator's validation or distancing.

As for the mediative, for the analysis of the corpus, we will return to the study by Guentcheva (1994) on which Adam (2011) refers to when he places this phenomenon among the categories that mark the ER. The author refers to the mediative to explain that certain language marks “allow the enunciator to signify the different degrees of distance he or she takes with respect to the described situations, since he or she has distinguished them in a mediated way.” (GUENTCHÉVA, 1994, p. 08, our translation). In addition, like Neves (2012), we assume that the mediative can be related to the epistemic modality, as it is situated in the domain of the not-right (representing the non-assumption or partial assumption, through epistemic verbs should, may; adverb perhaps) and for expressing the enunciative distance, since the S1/E1 resorts to another source to validate the utterance.

Referring precisely to the case of the mediative in French, with a focus on verb tenses, Guentchéva (1994) states that not all languages have specific grammatical units (morphemes) to mark the distance from S1/E (as is the case in Portuguese) and French, for example). Even so, varying from one language to another, this phenomenon can be expressed by semantic groups or words based on three values that indicate that the content of the point of view is dependent on another enunciative source, namely:

- 1) Facts reported: report of states or events – related to knowledge generally admitted or transmitted by tradition, by a third person or simply by heard;
- 2) Inferred facts: deduction, induction, abduction – refer to inferences resulting from observation and reasoning;
- 3) Facts of surprise: demonstration of astonishment or surprise – refers to the expression of administrative value.

Based on the author's theoretical reflections, we understand that each language can establish in its own grammatical system the way in which the enunciator will formally mark the degree of involvement in relation to the reported facts. The idea of degree suggests the possibility of a continuum, in which the different languages allow the enunciator to signal his or her engagement or detachment in relation to the situations described. In the case of the mediative, this involvement is one of detachment and does not require the enunciator's commitment to the truth or falsity of the reported facts, as it does not express his or her position on a speech act.

From this we can conclude that the enunciator does not assume responsibility for the content of the point of view.

6 (Re)construction of the news production context and the establishment of the text for analysis

The piece of news selected for the analysis in this article was published on February 17th, 2020, by Claudia magazine, being an update of the publication made on August 22nd, 2019, according to information from the newsroom, entered below the top of the news. This one has the title “Woman is prevented from getting into an app car because of her weight” and the subtitle “After the case, women gathered in Salvador to protest against fatphobia”.

The news circulated in online format and reports the case that occurred with Joyce dos Santos, who was prevented from getting into an app car because of her weight, which caused the reaction of other women, in protest against fatphobia. The case was thus designated in the news article: “an episode of fatphobia”.

Fatphobia is understood as the prejudice, intolerance or aversion against the fat body, which causes difficulties in different levels of life of the fat person in society, from social and psychological, in interpersonal relationships, as the lack of access to adequate health, transportation, clothing and places (seats in the most diverse places that fit these bodies).

Considering the origin of the text in question, both in the sense of being authored by a magazine aimed at the female audience and in its relationship with the social, historical and cultural surroundings, we can say that its thematic content raises the possibility for debates, to inscribe it at the heart of a problem facing today's society. Therefore, this element, in its intimate relationship with the compositional structure and the verbal style for the construction of the genre (BAKHTIN, 2016), is very relevant in the textual-discursive analysis that we propose.

Since the text does not exist outside the gaze we cast on it, and since its establishment is one of the first conditions to provide the analysis (ADAM, 2011, 2010), we will consider the version of the news available in online format and not its possible appearances in other media, either by the same magazine or by other sources.

7 Analysis of the corpus

Considering the contextual information presented, we reproduce below, in full, the text of the news clipped as a corpus of analysis in this work, for, then, making our notes of description of

the materiality of the saying and of the interpretation of the meaning effects, according to the proposed purposes.

Woman is prevented from getting into app car because of weight
After the case, women gathered in Salvador to protest against fatphobia

Joyce Santos went through an episode of fatphobia involving a 99 app driver, who denied taking her in his car because of her weight.

After ordering the car, Joyce noticed that the driver had passed the meeting point marked on the app and then sent a message through the platform asking what had happened. "How do you get past me? I call and you don't stop," she wrote. "Walk, dear, to lose weight.", replied the driver.

Last Sunday (18), the collective "There will be Fat Woman" gathered women in the streets of Salvador to protest against the case. The women took pictures on the beach, had a picnic and talked about the case.

The collective was created in 2016 with the aim of fighting fatphobia, increasing the self-esteem of fat women and demanding public policies in favor of social inclusion.

99's press office says that the driver is blocked in the application and that the company is willing to help the police in the investigation of the case. Read the clarification note in full:

99 received, through social networks, the serious report of the passenger Joyce dos Santos, who had her race refused by a driver of the platform. The company deeply regrets the situation, and reiterates that it repudiates any type of discrimination and has a zero-tolerance policy in relation to it.

99 guides and sensitizes its partner drivers to serve passengers with kindness and respect. In its terms of use, the company emphasizes that partner drivers cannot discriminate or select passengers for any reason, in addition to treating them with good faith, professionalism and respect.

A specialized team was mobilized to investigate Joyce's case and is seeking to contact the passenger to give her support and reception. Meanwhile, the driver was blocked. 99 is available to collaborate with the police investigation.

99 reiterates that it continually invests to prevent this type of situation. The company periodically organizes conversation circles to guide partner drivers to be respectful and kind to everyone. In addition, a new platform of courses for 100% of drivers focused on diversity and citizenship was launched and is available in person and online. The first module is about fighting LGBTQIA+ phobia. The next ones on harassment and racism will be available this month.

Passengers or drivers who have suffered any form of discrimination should immediately report it to the company, through its app or by calling 0800-888-8999, so that corrective measures can be taken. We work 24 hours a day, 7 days a week, to exclusively take care of the protection of users. 99 remains at your disposal for any clarification.

Source: Claudia website. Available at: <https://claudia.abril.com.br/noticias/mulher-impedida-entrar-carro-por-causa-do-peso/>.

Initially, we can highlight that the construction of the objects of discourse is based on the noun phrases referring to the 4 (four) main characters focused on the news: the woman (Joyce), the driver, the women (from the collective) and the 99 company. Resumption referents are not so varied throughout the text, with a repetition of these phrases or their replacement by oblique and personal pronouns, and, in the case of 99, the reference occurs mainly by the term company.

As for the modifiers related to these enunciators second (e2) focused in the text by the speaker-enunciator first (S1/E1 - representing the editorial team of Claudia magazine, responsible for the news), we have, in most of the highlighted examples, verbal circumstances of the predicates, which indicate aspects of the fight against fatphobia and discrimination suffered by the victim, as well as the repudiation of any type of discrimination. Next, we list the referents, designations, modifiers of predications attributed to them by the news text and the resulting Rd.

Table 3: The construction of Dr in the news about the fatphobia episode.

ENUNCIATIVE INSTANCE	DISCOURSE OBJECTS (REFERENTS)	REFERENTS DESIGNATION	PREDICATES AND MODIFIERS	DISCOURSEIVE REPRESENTATIONS (Dr)
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A Redação da revista Claudia	Woman	Joyce dos Santos Joyce	<i>Is prevented from entering na app car because of her weight.</i> <i>Suffered a fatphobia episode.</i>	Victim
	<i>A fatphobia episode</i>	The case	<i>[interdiction/prohibition] from entering na app car because of her weight.</i> <i>[refusal/denial to] take her in his car because of her weight.</i>	Fatphobia Social Exclusion
	A 99 app driver	The driver	<i>Denied taking her</i> <i>Passed by the meeting spot marked in the app.</i> <i>Is blocked in the app.</i>	Responsible for the case – the episode of fatphobia. Punishment target by the app and focus of the investigations on the case.
	The collective There Will Be Fat Woman	The collective	<i>Gathered women in the streets of Salvador to protest against the case.</i> <i>created in 2016 with the goal to fight against fatphobia, increase fat women self esteem and claim public policies for social inclusion.</i>	Responsible for conducting the case. Responsible for fighting against fatphobia, increase the public policies for social inclusion.
	Women [from the collective]	The women	<i>Gathered in Salvador to protest against fatphobia.</i> <i>Took pictures at the beach, made a picnic and talked about the case.</i>	Responsible for protesting against the case.
	Fat women	<i>The collective was created in 2016 with the goal to fight against fatphobia, increase fat women self esteem and claim public policies for social inclusion.</i>	-	Low self-esteem
	99- company	Legal advice of 99. The app The company	<i>Claims that the driver is banned from the app.</i> <i>states to be available to help the police in the case investigation.se dispõe a ajudar</i>	Responsible for the drivers' app. Responsible for punishing the driver. Ally in the investigations.

Source: elaborated by the authors.

From the point of view of the enunciative instance, the S1/E1, it is evident that it is an episode of fatphobia that had Joyce Santos as a victim and the driver of the 99 app as responsible. Discursively, the episode is represented as social exclusion, by the refusal of the driver to take the woman because of her weight (he “passed straight through”, did not stop the car). Thus, it was the condition of being a fat woman that made it impossible for her to access the transport service offered by the 99 app. The “case”, as it is called throughout the text, also resonates with prejudice or social discrimination, since a person received different treatment (inferior, negative) because of her weight, as attested by the driver's speech narrated by the woman herself in the complaint message and also reported in direct speech in the text of the news - "Walk, honey, to lose weight".

Due to the different Dr constructed via the designation of referents and modifiers attributed to them, we can say that, as regards the argumentative dimension, the news text goes beyond the language action (aimed or objective) of simply reporting a bad fact about injustice. The effectiveness of the journal's sociodiscursive action, that is, the act of illocutionary speech and argumentative orientation (ADAM, 2011), proceeds depending on different factors:

- i) first, by assimilating the magazine's character of putting on the agenda subjects of fundamental interest for women's lives, being, therefore, a discursive instance with supposed influence on the female world;
- ii) secondly, because it rises a certain tone of social denunciation from the two discursive representations built right in the title of the news – “Women are prevented from getting into an app car [Dr of exclusion] because of their weight” [Dr of prejudice or discrimination], which, in turn, are immediately associated with the Dr of fatphobia built around the topic addressed;
- iii) thirdly, by representing, through direct speech, the voices that are interested in being “heard” in the situation of social interaction in question – the voice of the fat woman given as a victim (in her legitimate questioning), that of the driver (in its act of exclusion/discrimination), that of the company responsible for the application (in its clarification and measures in the case);
- iv) and, finally, for staging an important voice in the text that merges with the interests of the S1/E1, effected through the two photographs related to the protest, especially the one with the hashtags #there will be fat and #respect.

Apparently, then, the reader finds in the context itself the necessary data to interpret the episode that happens with Joyce as an explicit case of fatphobia. The significant chain of the text, materialized under the mediation of at least two semiosis (the written text and the two relatively

large images), leaves no room for doubt about this. By the way, Adam (2011, p. 53) himself states that “if the co-text is available and if it proves to be sufficient, the interpretant will not need to look elsewhere”.

It is not by chance that the word fatphobia appears in 03 (three) distinct and relevant moments of the text: 1) below the title of the news, corroborating the reading that it suggests; 2) in the opening paragraph of the episode's narration, bringing information related to “what”, “where”, “how”, “with whom”; and 3) in the statement that precedes the closing of the narrative, when it deals with the social movement that manifested itself against the case. In these terms, the “episode” is emphatically attributed the modifying element “of fatphobia”, which is validated as such by the reactions of other fat women in protest.

The socio-historical, political, cultural and ideological surroundings of this news demand us to know that Claudia magazine can be thought of as one of the many discursive instances within the media with the power to report cases of social injustice and that, in doing so, it places its points of view in the direction of several other guidelines of general interest. But it is from the place of a women's magazine that this force operates more impetuously, as this socio-discursive formation reconfigures the identity of women in new scenarios of modern society, which makes them increasingly aspire and fight for independence, freedom and power.

In this direction, we observe that the Dr constructed in the text due to the episode of fatphobia narrated in the news are supported by a network of interdiscursive relationships, in such a way that allows us to construct the following meaning effects: fat women are victims of social exclusion and discrimination ; this social group lies in a situation of low self-esteem and vulnerability, to the point of having to fight for social justice and lack the support and reception of other fronts of struggle (movements, groups or entities, such as the collective “There will be fat” and company 99); episodes of fatphobia need to be reported (as Joyce did when sending a message to the app) and, above all, have the appropriate measures taken by the competent bodies or sectors (blocking the driver, clarifying the public and investigating the case, in the case of the company).

The conditions of news production, therefore, authorize us to understand that episodes of fatphobia need to gain greater proportions and reach general knowledge, when notified by social media. It is at this point that the textual materiality of the news builds a positive Rd of Claudia magazine itself, for echoing her voice, established in the socio-ideological place of a feminist

magazine attentive to the agenda of modernity and the agenda for the coming years, with regard to peace, social justice and the efficiency of institutions.

In its “objective enunciation” (RABATEL, 2016a), but not impartial or neutral (VOLÓCHINOV, 2017), the news text stages a prototypical way of managing other voices in genres of this nature, as well as the organization of texture and text plan (ADAM, 2011), compositional structure, verbal style (BAKHTIN, 2016), among other aspects. However, as we have already alluded to, this is not done by chance. The entire content of the text is expressed in the so-called objective, impersonal language, evidencing the enunciative distance on the part of the person who wrote it, in a style specific to the genre. It is not an author (a specific journalist) who is at the source of the reported points of view, but a discursive instance, the newsroom, which allows us to infer that it is a manifestation of collective enunciative responsibility, due to the fact that the authorship of the news be represented by all those who make up the magazine. From a legal point of view, we know that the magazine team is also responsible for everything they said.

There are some passages in the text that indicate the presence of a mediator (mediative) frame and of the perceptive focus (ADAM, 2011), meaning that this S1/E1 is not responsible for the reported content, namely: Joyce's message, the driver's speech addressed to her and the clarification note issued by the Advisory of 99. In relation to the women of the collective, we have the mediation in fact reported, as the editorial staff of the magazine attributes the saying and actions to the collective, reporting what was done after the case with Joyce. In these linguistic contexts, we have the imputation of points of view, due to the fact that the S1/E1 attributes the reported propositional content to others (RABATEL, 2016a). The sayings and facts are, therefore, attributed to these 04 (four) characters presented throughout the news.

Still regarding the enunciative responsibility, we say that the enunciation of S1/E1 is neither impartial nor indifferent to the content addressed. Even in the apparent objectivity, certain linguistic choices for the construction of points of view reveal subjective engagement, that is, a socio-ideological position on the case. In the news, we see that the form of engagement borders on “teaching by example”, working discursively as a kind of call for women and society as a whole to unite in the fight against fatphobia. The table below demonstrates how the linguistic choices that express the points of view provoke the engagement or the enunciative distance of the L1/E1 in the news text. Understanding that there may be variations in the continuum of manifestation of subjectivity in language, we signal with “+” the passages that reveal more engagement or more distance.

Table 4: Manifestation of subjectivity by the speaker-enunciator first in the management of points of view

Focused enunciative instance	Linguistic marks in the news text	Specification of marks	Manifestation of subjectivity by S1/E1	
			+ <i>Engaged</i>	+ <i>Detached</i>
S1/E1	S1/E1 episode of fatphobia;; Read the clarification note.	Expression with negative connotation; verb in the imperative.	x	
Joyce Santos	is prevented; because of the weight; because of her weight; She noticed that the driver had passed by; “How do you get past me? I call and you don't stop,' she wrote.	Verb and expressions with negative connotations; question (intersubjective mode).	x	
The app driver	denied taking her, “Walk, dear, to lose weight,' replied the driver.	opinionated verb; affective lexeme in an ironic sense.		x
The fat women from the collective	The fat women of the collective gathered; protest the case; they took pictures on the beach, had a picnic and talked about the case.	Deontic value (challenge).	x	
The clarification note of the 99 serious report;	The clarification note of the 99 serious report; race denied; platform driver; deeply regrets reiterates that it repudiates any form of discrimination; zero tolerance policy; sensitizes its drivers; kindness and respect; partner drivers may not discriminate or select passengers for any reason; treat them with good faith, professionalism and respect; mobilized to investigate the case; support and reception; the driver was blocked; available to collaborate with the police investigation;	Evaluative and affective lexemes, names and expressions with negative or positive connotations; imperative verb with objective modal value (ought).	x	

	continually invests to prevent this type of situation; periodically holds conversation circles; posture of respect and kindness towards everyone; guides and sensitizes; focus on diversity and citizenship; combating LGBTQphobia; must report immediately to the company; corrective measures; exclusively to protect users; remains at your disposal for any clarification.		
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The choice to report the episode suffered by Joyce and, at the same time, the protest carried out by the collective, also bringing, in full, the company's clarification note, makes the magazine indirectly demonstrate its agreement with the point of view of repudiation to the case and with the understanding that fatphobia must be fought. In this sense, if we consider the totality of signs (verbal and imagery) that make up the co(n)text of the news, we see very clearly that it expresses the posture of co-enunciation (RABATEL, 2016b) in relation to the points of view of the enunciators according to the ones focused on the text – Joyce's, the fat women's and the company's. As a result, S1/E1 seems to agree with the fat women's act of protest and with the action taken by the application to block the driver and investigate the case.

In the opposite direction to the driver's speech – caught in an ironic and rude tone by the linguistic variety used and faithfully reported via direct speech –, the points of view built throughout the news do not issue any value judgment in relation to the fat body, nor do they express the co-enunciation in a shown/marked way with expressions such as "I am against him", "I agree with her", etc. It is in the inseparable relationship with the context of speech production that the material dimension of the text allows the interpretation of movements of (non) assumption of enunciative responsibility by L1/E1 in the face of the imputed points of view.

By propagating the news in the way it did, the magazine indirectly makes it known that it does not share situations of social exclusion and discrimination, nor disrespect. Positioning this news in a dialogic interaction with the historically situated network of meanings, the magazine, as

a representative journalistic media of the female world, reflects a collective point of view eminently against episodes of fatphobia and favorable to the struggles to combat them.

Final Considerations

Considering our purpose of a co(n)textual analysis of the meanings constructed from the materiality of the news published in online format about an episode of fatphobia, we reiterate the importance of studying the text centered on the semantic-pragmatic, enunciative and socio-discursive levels, in an articulation between the planes of analysis of text and discourse. This type of analysis allows us to reflect on how the speaker-enunciator mobilizes strategic procedures of textualization (such as the choice and ordering of the lexicon), how he or she manages the voices of other enunciators, how he or she constructs the discursive representation of the objects of discourse and how he or she signals enunciative responsibility.

Consequently, the paths of our analysis corroborate the hypothesis that lexical choices (referential, verbal, circumstantial) are carried out in an organized way, in order to establish an argumentative orientation of the text. These semantic choices and the supposedly distanced construction of expression of the (non) assumption of enunciative responsibility, through the mediative, show that, in relation to the news, the choices are not neutral, but are rather conveyed to the interests of the participants of the interaction. Thus, there is an intended construction of meanings about fatphobia and other forms of discrimination, in addition to not blaming the company for what happened, in a demonstration that this type of practice is structural, historically naturalized.

Within the limits of its theoretical and methodological scope, the study of discursive representations and enunciative responsibility, as presented here, intends to contribute to a better understanding of these enunciative devices and to a critical reading of the different discourses, observing how the forms of exclusion verbalize social discrimination and how they react to it, whether legitimizing it or fighting it

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